

Research Article

Causes and Consequences of Examination Malpractice on the Academic Achievement of Office Technology and Management Students in Polytechnics in South-Western Zone of Nigeria¹Abimbola Olunike Adegbenjo and ²Tunde Olusesan Adebayo¹Office Technology and Management Department, The Federal Polytechnic, Ede, Osun State.²Department of Business Education, Federal College of Education (SP) Oyo, Oyo StateCorresponding Author: abimbolanikeadegbenjo@gmail.com**Abstract**

This paper examined causes and consequences of examination malpractice on the academic achievement of Office Technology and Management (OTM) students in Polytechnics in South-Western zone of Nigeria. The population of the study comprised all HND I and HND II in the five States and four Federal Polytechnics offering OTM in South-Western zone of Nigeria. Through random sampling method, three States and two Federal Polytechnics were selected as sample for the study. A total of 512 HND I and HND II students were eventually selected out of 682 students through stratified sampling method. Questionnaire was the major instrument used to gather data for the study; while, mean and standard deviation were used to analyse the data gathered. It was found that government non-implementation of examination malpractice decree and inadequate preparation for examinations were some of the causes of examination malpractices; also, the study confirmed that irreversible loss of credibility and dismissal from school were the consequences of examination malpractice on OTM students and that implementation of examination malpractice decree and adequate preparation for examinations among others were the ways of minimizing or eliminating examination malpractices among OTM students. It was recommended that government should endeavour to implement examination malpractice Act No 33 of 1999 which stipulated a minimum punishment of ₦50,000 and a maximum of five years imprisonment without option of fine for students who involved in examination malpractices. If the government implements this Act, examination malpractices may be minimized or eliminated totally and that students should endeavour to prepare adequately for examinations by developing effective study s before, during and after the examination in order to excel in their studies.

Keywords: Examination, Examination malpractice, causes, consequences, OTM programme, Polytechnics

Received: 12/07/17

Accepted: 01/10/17

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ISSN: 2251 - 0486 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

Introduction

Examination is a means of assessment to test the knowledge, skills and abilities of students. In schools, examination is a means of evaluating the quantity of knowledge, skills and abilities acquired within a specified period of time. Nnam and Inah (2015) saw examination as a yardstick against which candidates' competencies and progresses are formally measured and appraised in the education sector. Teaching and learning become more efficient and effective when students are subjected to examination processes in order to determine the rate of assimilation of contents of the instruction given. The teachers also use examinations to assess the level of their performances. Examination may be administered in form of verbal or non-verbal; that is, in written form, gesture or sign (in a confined area that requires an examinee to physically perform a set of skills) and it can also be administered on computer. Today, many higher institutions in Nigeria conduct examinations with the aid of computers; that is, Computer-Based Tests (CBT). However, despite the importance of examination in teaching and learning processes, a number of factors may likely affect the credibility of examination scores. One of such practices that may affect the reliability of examination scores is examination malpractice.

Examination malpractice is any dishonest or unauthorised action or deed committed by a student on his own or in collaboration with others like fellow students, guardians, parents, teachers, head teachers, examination officials, supervisors, invigilators, security officers and anybody or group of people before, during or after examination in order to obtain underserved marks or grades (Onuka and Durowoju, 2013). Examination malpractice does not occur in the examination hall alone, it occurs before, during and even after the examination. The incidences of examination malpractice are common everywhere and every examination season witnesses the new and ingenious ways of cheating.

Scholars found that examination malpractice is always in form of copying on sheets of paper, handkerchiefs, desk/chairs; swapping of answer booklets and collusion with other candidates or external agents. Others include leakage of examination questions before the actual examination day, use of electronic gadgets like calculators, organizers, radio walkman and mobile phones. Also, bringing books or cribs into the hall, insulting or assaulting supervisor or invigilator, replacement of answer script with another one during or after the examination, impersonation, smuggling scripts written outside into the examination hall, writing on thigh, stretching of neck like the Giraffe to look at the work of fellow candidates, hooligans gaining entry into the examination hall by force when examination is in progress to remove question paper, relaxation of vigilance by

invigilators, talking, dictation of answers to students among others (Adeyemi, 2010; Akanni and Odojin, 2015; Onyibe, Uma and Ibina, 2015).

Examination malpractice occurs at all levels of the Nigerian educational sector. It is sad that teachers, parents, management of institutions or school authorities, office clerks, invigilators or supervisors, officials of various examination bodies, police officers and bank officials; that is, custodians of examination materials are in most cases the perpetrators of examination malpractices. Ojerinde in Emaikwu (2012) asserted that examination malpractice is already becoming a culture in Nigerian educational scene because it is being condoned by most parents, students, teachers and lecturers.

It is disheartening that examinations are not achieving their primary objectives; examination malpractice had become a nauseating phenomenon in the Nigerian education system which is posing a great threat to the standard of examinations in Nigeria and the acceptability of the worth of the certificates resulting from the examinations. The problem of examination malpractice has reduced certificates issued in Nigeria into worthless papers, such that a number of candidates with outstanding results cannot defend their certificates.

Although, the Nigerian government has enacted the Examination Malpractice Act for anyone involved in examination malpractice. Examination Malpractice Acts No. 33, of 1999 stipulates a minimum punishment of fifty thousand naira (N50,000) and a maximum of five years imprisonment, without option of fine, for violators of the offences stipulated in the Act. The offences are: cheating at examinations, impersonation, inordinance at examinations, disturbances at examinations, misconduct at examinations, obstruction of supervisors, forgery of result slips, breach of duties, conspiracy and aiding, conviction for alternative offences, offences by bodies corporate, miscellaneous among others. In Nigeria, a lot of measures had been put in place by government, examination bodies, institutions, school authorities, civil societies, well-meaning individuals and other stakeholders to eradicate examination malpractices but all efforts seem not to have yielded positive results; instead, the problem seems spreading across Nigeria with all forms of sophistication. Corroborating this, Omemu (2015) stated that the irony of it all is that despite the several attempts made by school authorities, government agencies, parents and church leaders in trying to educate the Nigerian students on the evils of examination malpractices, these abnormalities are still on the increase in various schools.

Office Technology and Management (OTM) students in Nigerian Polytechnics may not be exempted from examination malpractice despite the peculiarity of OTM programme in skill development. Office Technology and Management is a programme designed by

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the National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) to replace the Secretarial Studies programme which has been in operation since 1989. The objectives of Office Technology and Management programme are to provide the technical knowledge and vocational skills for commercial and economic development; give training and impart the necessary skills to the individual who wants to be self-reliant economically. Office Technology and Management programme is also to equip students with secretarial/office skills for employment in various fields of endeavour. In addition to the acquisition of vocational skills, the students are equipped with effective work competencies and socio-psychological work skills which are very essential in everyday interactions with others (NBTE, 2004). The main goal of OTM programme is to develop employability skills in the recipients in order to be self-reliant. Any OTM student who involved in examination malpractice may not be able to develop required skills for self-employment, which may eventually hinder such a student to acquire desired office job or perform as expected in self-owned business. It is observed that organisations are in need of qualified secretaries that can perform efficiently and effectively on the job but any OTM student involved in examination malpractice in Nigerian Polytechnics may not be able to complete his or her studies and may likely lack secretarial or office skills which is required in every office, and may lead to underemployment or loss of job.

Based on this background, this paper examines the causes and consequences of examination malpractices on the academic achievement of OTM students in Polytechnics in South-western zone of Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following questions were raised to guide the study:

- 1) What are the causes of examination malpractices among OTM students?
- 2) What are the consequences of examination malpractices on OTM students?
- 3) What are the ways of minimizing or eliminating examination malpractices among OTM students?

Literature Review

Examinations could also be seen as the most objective techniques used in the measurement of learning outcomes at all levels of education in Nigeria and the world over (Zakka, 2014). Examinations could also be seen as the measurement of proficiency in knowledge and skills, either in oral or written forms, and evaluating the adequacies of these properties possessed by candidates (Animasahun and Ogunniran, 2014). Also, Kpangban, Ajaja and Umedhe (2008) defined examination as an assessment intended to measure knowledge, skill, attitude, physical fitness or classification in many other topics such as beliefs. Therefore, examination can be seen as a form of evaluation with the aim of examining learners' level of skill acquisition after a given training. It can also be seen as a formal test of a person's knowledge or proficiency in a subject.

Examination malpractice is any illegal act committed by a student single handedly or in collaboration with others; like fellow students, parents, teachers, supervisors, invigilators, printers and anybody or group of people before, during or after examination in order to obtain undeserved marks or grades (Wilayat, 2009). Kpangban, Ajaja and Umudhe (2008) defined examination malpractice as an action or inaction by students, teachers, school heads, examination invigilators or supervisors and officials of examination bodies that leads to a student having an unmerited result. Therefore, examination malpractice can be seen as a social behaviour which is contrary to the rules and regulations governing such examination demonstrated by a candidate charged with the conduct of examination. It can also be referred to as illicit acts which contravene the rules and practices guiding the examination with the aim of obtaining good results by fraudulent means.

Akanni and Odojin (2015) divided examination malpractice into three; that is, pre-examination, during examination and post examination. In the pre-examination category, it is the procurement of question papers prior to the date of examination. Malpractice during examination includes: copying from another candidate, impersonation, collusion by interested parties with invigilators and supervisors, substitution of scripts of registered examinees with those done by mercenaries and so on. Post examination malpractices on the other hand include those traced to the full-time staff of the examination council in a situation where invigilators and supervisors substituted unearned scores with earned ones; leading to inflated scores. Candidates with such ill-gotten grades get admission to higher institutions where they are found to perform below expectations.

Consequently, examination malpractice is perpetrated for different reasons and it affects the credibility of results in the sense that grades are assigned to candidates wrongly

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thereby misleading the teacher and other users of the school products in decision making. The major reason for this, according to Olushola (2006) is overdependence on certificates. Animasahun and Ogunniran (2014) in their study 'correlate of examination malpractice among secondary school students in Oyo State' found that government non-implementation of examination malpractices decree, lack of effective supervision of students during examinations, society preference for paper qualification, inadequate preparation for examination, lack of self-confidence, ill-equipped school and lack of good study habits are the causes of examination malpractices. According to Anzene (2014), the root causes of examination malpractice include the following: inadequate teaching and learning facilities such as classrooms, libraries and laboratories; poor moral upbringing of some youths by parents, students quick emphasis on success and wealth without a corresponding emphasis on legitimate means and avenues to be used positively in achieving success, incessant strikes and admission of unqualified candidates. Furthermore, Adeyemi (2010) found that indiscipline among students that made many of them to be involved in examination malpractices is one of the major causes of examination malpractices. Oseni (2014) listed the followings as the factors influencing examination malpractices: poor teaching methods and lack of completion of the required syllabus, high expectation, low salary level, high enrolment fees and unconducive environment. Finally, Furo (2015) found that antisocial behaviour and sitting arrangement are the factors contributing to examination malpractices.

According to Zakka (2014) the followings are the consequences of examination malpractices: decreases job efficiency, denies innocent students the opportunity for admission, delays the processing of examination results and stunts national growth. Anzene (2014) listed the followings as the effects of examination malpractices: dismissal, loss of position and irreversible loss of credibility. Termination, loss of self-confidence and certificate racketeering are the effects of examination malpractices on national development as identified by Onyibe, Uma and Ibina, 2015. Also, Kpangban, Ajala and Umudhe (2008) found that the major effects of examination malpractices are reduction in the quality and standard of education in the country, and high educational wastage as those who cheat to pass examinations at lower levels achieve very poorly at higher levels. Others are: inability to defend one's certificates, lack of skills, knowledge and ability to perform expected duties, and examination malpractices discourage other students from hard work; that is, from studying very well for the examinations.

Though, various researchers had conducted studies on examination malpractices but none of them studied Office Technology and Management students in Nigerian Polytechnics in the South-Western zone of Nigeria, which is the area this study explored into and that is the gap this paper tried to fill.

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Methodology

Survey research design was adopted in this study and the population comprised six hundred and eighty two (682) HND I and HND II students in all the States and Federal Polytechnics offering OTM in South-Western zone of Nigeria. There are four Federal Polytechnics and five State Polytechnics offering OTM in the South-Western zone of Nigeria and they all served as the population for the study. Through random sampling method, Federal Polytechnic Ilaro, Federal Polytechnic Ede, Rufus Giwa Polytechnic, Owo, Lagos State Polytechnic, and Ibadan Polytechnic; that is, two Federal and three States Polytechnics were selected as sample. Due to large number of subjects, 580 HND I and HND II students were selected through stratified sampling method out of 682 students representing 85% of the population. A 30 items questionnaire titled 'Examination Malpractice Questionnaire (EMQ) was developed to elicit data for the study. The participants responded to the statements on a four point Likert scale. To ensure face and content validity three experts in Business Education and Measurement and Evaluation validated the instrument. Their suggestions resulted in the final instrument. The split-half method was adopted for the reliability test; while, the Spearman Brown's formula was applied to correlate the two parts resulting in a reliability coefficient 0.83. Of the 580 copies of the questionnaire distributed, 512 were returned. This gave a percentage return of 88.

In analyzing the data collected; the mean (\bar{X}) and standard deviation (SD) were the statistical tools used. The mean (\bar{X}) of 2.50 was used for the decision, such that a mean rating on any item by the respondents equal to or above 2.50 was taken as "Agree"; while, any mean rating lower than 2.50 was taken as "Disagree".

Results

Research Question 1: What are the causes of examination malpractice among OTM students?

Table 1: Mean ratings and standard deviations of respondents on causes of examination malpractice

S/N	ITEMS	RESPONSES		RMKS
		\bar{x}	S.D.	
1	Government non-implementation of examination malpractice decree	3.27	.698	High
2	Lack of effective supervision of students during examinations	3.59	.560	High
3	Inadequate preparation for examinations	3.59	.801	High
4	Inadequate teaching and learning facilities and resources	3.55	.660	High
5	Poor moral upbringing of some youths by parents	3.36	.569	High
6	Indiscipline	3.23	.849	High
7	Poor teaching methods	2.96	1.119	High
8	Antisocial behaviour	3.16	.851	High
9	Peer group influence	3.16	.930	High
10	Laziness	3.66	.661	High
	Total	33.53	7.698	

Source: Field study, 2016

The data presented in table 1 revealed that the mean ratings of the items ranged from 2.96 to 3.66. All the items had their means above the cut-off points of 2.50 which indicated that the respondents agreed that all the items were causes of examination malpractices on academic achievement of OTM students. The standard deviation of the items ranged from .560 to 1.119. The relatively low standard deviation values confirmed that the respondents were close in their opinions.

Research Question 2: What are the consequences of examination malpractice on OTM students?

Table 2: Mean ratings and standard deviations of respondents on consequences of examination malpractice

S/N	ITEMS	RESPONSES		RMKS
		\bar{x}	S.D.	
11	Reduce quality and standard of education	3.52	.527	High
12	Loss of position	3.30	.551	High
13	Irreversible loss of credibility	3.31	.738	High
14	Dismissal from school	3.45	.744	High
15	Loss of self-confidence	3.25	.889	High
16	Discouraging other students from hard work	3.13	.912	High
17	Breeds generations of fraudsters and other social vices	3.31	.777	High
18	Decreases job efficiency	3.23	.867	High
19	Inability to defend one's certificates	3.50	.699	High
20	Lack of skills, knowledge and ability to perform expected duties	3.59	.581	High
	Total	33.59	7.285	

Source: Field study, 2016

Table 2 showed that the mean ratings of the items ranged from 3.13 to 3.59. All the items had their means above the cut-off points of 2.50 which indicated that the respondents agreed that all the items were consequences of examination malpractices on academic achievement of OTM students. The standard deviation of the items ranged from .527 to .912. The relatively low standard deviation values ascertained that the respondents were not too far apart in their opinions.

Research Question 3: What are the ways of minimizing or eliminating examination malpractice among OTM students?

Table 3: Mean ratings and standard deviations of respondents on ways of minimizing or eliminating examination malpractice

S/N	ITEMS	RESPONSES		RMKS
		\bar{x}	S.D.	
21	Provision of adequate resources and facilities for teaching and learning	3.65	.523	High
22	Adequate preparation for examinations	3.70	.529	High
23	Implementation of examination malpractice decree	3.44	.626	High
24	Inculcation of moral values and instructions	3.44	.727	High
25	Effective supervision by the invigilators	3.41	.638	High
26	Qualified personnel should be employed in teaching profession	3.49	.680	High
27	Publication of names of students involved in examination malpractice in Newspapers	3.27	.674	High
28	Provision of guidance and counselling service	3.49	.607	High
29	Students involved in examination malpractice should be expelled from school	3.57	.495	High
30	Teachers should undergo training, workshops and seminars from time to time	3.56	.497	High
	Total	35.02	5.996	

Source: Field study, 2016

The data presented in Table 3 showed that the mean ratings of the items ranged from 3.27 to 3.70. All the items had their means above the cut-off points of 2.50 which indicated that the respondents agreed that all the items were ways of eliminating examination malpractices among OTM students. The standard deviation of the items ranged from .495 to .727. The relatively low standard deviation values established that the respondents were not very divergent in their responses.

Discussion of Findings

The study found that government non-implementation of examination malpractice decree, lack of effective supervision of students during examinations and inadequate preparation for examinations are causes of examination malpractices on academic

achievement of OTM students. These findings are in line with the study of Animasahun and Ogunniran (2014) who found that government non-implementation of examination malpractices decree, lack of effective supervision of students during examinations, societal preferences for paper qualifications, inadequate preparation for examinations, lack of self-confidence, ill-equipped school and lack of good study habits are the causes of examination malpractices. The reason for this may likely be as a result of non-implementation of examination malpractice decree which states that any individual involved in examination malpractice should pay a minimum amount of ₦50,000 and a maximum of 5 years imprisonment without option of fine. The study also confirmed that inadequate teaching and learning facilities and resources and poor moral upbringing of some youths by parents are the causes of examination malpractice. These findings are consistent with previous research findings as reported by Anzene (2014) who found that inadequate teaching and learning facilities such as classrooms, libraries and laboratories; poor moral upbringing of some youths by parents, students quick emphasis on success and wealth without a corresponding emphasis on legitimate means and avenues to be used positively in achieving success, incessant strikes and admission of unqualified candidates are the root causes of examination malpractice. The reason for this may likely be due to the fact that some institutions lack adequate teaching and learning facilities and resources and this may likely hinder the students from acquiring the required knowledge, skills and abilities needed to excel in examinations and on the jobs. Additionally, the study confirmed that indiscipline is one of the causes of examination malpractice among OTM students. This finding is in agreement with the study of Adeyemi (2010) who established that indiscipline among students that made many of them to be involved in examination malpractice is one of the major causes of examination malpractices. Furthermore, poor teaching methods were found to be one of the causes of examination malpractice among OTM students. This finding is consistent with the view of Oseni (2014) who listed poor teaching methods and lack of completion of the required syllabus, high expectation, low salary level, high enrolment fees and unconducive environment as the factors influencing examination malpractice. This might be due to the fact that some teachers were not trained. Some of them found themselves in teaching profession because they could not secure their desired jobs. Therefore, they could not perform efficiently and effectively on their jobs. The study also found that antisocial behaviours were some of the causes of examination malpractice. This finding was supported by the study of Furo (2015) who found that antisocial behaviours and sitting arrangements were some of the factors contributing to examination malpractice. The reason for this may likely be attributed to the fact that any student who is involved in anti-social behaviour may be occupied by such illicit acts and may not likely have enough time for his or her studies. Finally, the study established that peer group influence and laziness were the causes of examination malpractice among OTM students. The reason

for this may likely be due to the fact that some students prefer playing and chatting with friends to studying their books which may negatively affect their academic achievement.

It was found that examination malpractice reduces quality and standard of education. This is consistent with the study of Kpangban, Ajala and Umudhe (2008) who found that the major effects of examination malpractice are reduction in the quality and standard of education in the country, and high educational wastage as those who cheat to pass examinations at a lower level achieve very poorly at a higher level. It was also revealed that loss of position, irreversible loss of credibility and dismissal from school are the consequences of examination malpractice. These findings are in line with the study of Anzene (2014) who noted that loss of position, irreversible loss of credibility and dismissal from school are the effects of examination malpractice. The reason for this might be due to the fact that students involved in examination malpractice may certainly lose their positions, credibility and eventually may be dismissed from school because the secret will be unveiled or revealed one day. It was found however that, loss of self-confidence is one of the consequences of examination malpractice. This finding is supported by Onyibe, Uma and Ibina (2015) who asserted that termination, loss of self-confidence and certificate racketeering are the effects of examination malpractice on national development. The reason for this may likely be due to the fact that anyone who involved in examination malpractice will not have inner conviction that the result belongs to him/her. The study also revealed that examination malpractice breeds generations of fraudsters and other social vices. This finding is in agreement with the study of Emaikwu (2012) who found that breeding a generation of fraudsters and other social vices are the influences of examination malpractice on students. This might be attributed to the fact that examination malpractice is a fraudulent acts and anybody involved in them will see nothing bad in examination malpractice; and may also encourage others to involve in examination malpractice; and thereby breeding generations of fraudsters. Additionally, the study confirmed that examination malpractice decreases job efficiency. This is supported by Zakka (2014) who found that examination malpractice decreases job efficiency, denies innocent students the opportunity for admission, delays the processing of examination results and stunts national growth. The reason for this may likely be due to the fact that anyone who involved in examination malpractice may not be effective and efficient on the job. However, it was also found that examination malpractice discouraged other students from hard work; that is, from studying very well for the examination, inability to defend one's certificates, and lack of skills, knowledge and ability to perform expected duties are the consequences of examination malpractice on academic achievement of OTM students. The reason for this might be attributed to the fact that students who involved in examination malpractice when in school may not be able to defend their certificates

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ISSN: 2251 - 0486

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because the skills, knowledge and ability that is likely to be the proof of the certificates may not be there.

The study found that provision of adequate resources and facilities for teaching and learning, adequate preparation for examinations, implementation of examination malpractice decree, inculcation of moral values and instructions, effective supervision by the invigilators, employment of qualified personnel in teaching profession, publication of names of students involved in examination malpractice in newspapers, provision of guidance and counselling service, expulsion from school and organisation of training, workshops and seminars for the teachers are the ways of minimizing or eliminating examination malpractice among OTM students.

Conclusion

There is need for all relevant stakeholders such as: parents, teachers, school authorities, office clerks, invigilators or supervisors, officials of various examination bodies, and students among others to put necessary machineries in place in order to minimise or eliminate totally examination malpractice among OTM students in Nigerian Polytechnics because if not properly addressed; examination malpractice may lead to dismissal from school, breeds generations of fraudsters and other social vices, and irreversible loss of credibility among others.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations were proffered:

- 1) Nigerian government should provide adequate resources and facilities for teaching and learning in order to make teaching and learning processes to be more effective and efficient.
- 2) Government should endeavour to implement examination malpractice Act No 33 of 1999 which stipulated a minimum punishment of ₦50,000 and a maximum of five years imprisonment without option of fine for students that involved in examination malpractice. If the government implement this decree, examination malpractice may be minimized or eliminated totally. Also, government should publish the names of students involved in examination malpractice in newspapers to serve as deterrent for others.
- 3) Government should employ qualified personnel in the teaching profession; the issue of godfatherism should be stopped during recruitment exercises.

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Government should also organise trainings, workshops and seminars for the teachers from time to time in order to enhance their performances on the jobs.

- 4) Teachers should be disciplined, effective and efficient when invigilating in order not to encourage examination malpractice among the students in the examination halls.
- 5) Students should endeavour to prepare adequately for examinations by developing effective study habits before, during and after the examinations in order to excel in their studies.
- 6) Parents should inculcate moral values and instructions in their children; children that have been taught by the parents not to involve in examination malpractice may not be easily influenced by peer group.
- 7) Management of institutions or school authorities should employ counsellors in order to provide guidance and counselling services for the students from time to time on examination malpractice and other issues that affect them. Also, management of institutions should endeavour to expel students involved in examination malpractice from school in order to stop such misbehaviours.

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